

TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS OF HIGHER SECONDARY TEACHERS

Dr. A. C. Lal Kumar

Assistant Professor, G.E.T College of Education, Gudiyattam, Vellore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. A. C. Lal Kumar, "Teachers Effectiveness of Higher Secondary Teachers", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Page Number 66-69, Volume 1, Issue 1, 2016.

Abstract:

Education is a nation building task and the process of education is largely lies in the hands of teacher. In the formal education system, infrastructure, finance and community support was provided by Government and stakeholders of education. But the process of molding the future citizens of India depends upon the quality of teacher. Effective teaching is a par excellence attribute of quality education. An effective teacher may be understood as one who helps in the development of basic skills, understanding, proper work habits, desirable attitude and value judgment. Teacher effectiveness concerns with these outcomes and the objectives of education. This study has the focus on the gap between the teacher effectiveness and quality education at secondary level. A sample of 300 higher secondary teachers from Vellore district has been selected for this study. Teacher Effectiveness Scale by Umme Dixit (1993). It is a five point scale and the reliability value of the tool was found as 0.89, and the validity was found to be 0.94. The data were analyzed for (i) gender (ii) type of management (iii) nature of school (iv) location of school and (v) marital status. The findings are the teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teacher's shows that there is no significant difference with respect to the gender, type of management, nature of school, location of school and marital status.

Keys Words: Teacher Effectiveness & Higher Secondary Teachers

Introduction:

According to the saying, "No system can raise above the level of its teachers", the quality of education depends totally on its teachers. The government is responsible for appointing the qualified teachers for the system. At present, in addition to their necessary qualification for teachers, the candidates have to get enough scoring in Teacher Eligibility Test conducted by either Central or State level has become mandatory by "Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act 2009". As far as the classroom transactions are concerned, teacher has to follow various methodologies and techniques to make the children understand the concepts. As per National Curriculum Framework 2005, the concept learnt within the four walls of a classroom has to be linked with the life outside the classroom and vice-versa. In a country like India which is rural and backward in its nature, depends greatly on the competence and effectiveness of its teachers. A wide range of skills and competencies are necessary for a teacher, to perform his/her functions in an effective manner. The teacher is expected to be a role model, good scholar, passionate, task manager and facilitator for an effective classroom transaction. Unless the teacher is effective, all efforts put for quality education will go waste. Teachers are expected to reach students by all means for the successful transaction of subject matter. The teacher plays highly significant role in every individual's life. Only profession which is capable of producing experts in various fields like Medicine, Engineering, Scientist, Poet, Writers, Journalists, and Teachers etc. is teaching profession. Hence achievement of children in various fields demands effectiveness of teachers.

Teacher Effectiveness:

In order to identify an effective teacher, the role and contribution of the teacher to the product of education needs to be examined. This enfold that good teacher should possess the knowledge of learner's characteristics, learning process, classroom management, requisite skills to be able to contribute significantly to the outcome of educational process which is the growth of students in the right direction. There are many activities in this respect. The effectiveness of the educational system largely depends upon the active, resourceful and competent teachers. An effective teacher not only imparts the entire educational curricula allotted to him in the best and most efficient manner but also ensures the best possible academic performance and an optimum development of the personalities among children. In the present scenario when there is a fierce competition in every sphere of life, effectiveness of teachers becomes imperative to empower the students for facing the emerging challenges of global world.

Effective teaching is a par excellence attribute of quality education. An effective teacher may be understood as one who helps in the development of basic skills, understanding, proper work habits, desirable attitude and value judgment. Teacher effectiveness concerns with these outcomes and the objectives of education. It aims at the effects of a teacher in the classroom situation. Teaching in the classroom depends upon how the teacher performs. According to Southern (1974), an effective teacher is the one who has a sense of humor, ability to explain things clearly so that students can easily understand what is being taught, ability to make any subject interesting to learn, ability to control the class, ability to be ready and willing to help students when they need and ability to be as fair as possible in dealing with students. In the words of Anderson (1991) "An effective teacher is the one who is quite consistently achieves goals, which either directly or indirectly

focuses on the learning of his/her students.” The positive and negative behaviors exhibited by teachers determine, to a great extent, their effectiveness in the classroom and, ultimately, the impact they have on student achievement.

Need for the Study:

Today's competitive world demands good quality in every field; schools and students are not an exception to it. Teacher effectiveness is an important factor which influences quality education. In spite of all other facilities like infrastructure, content materials, teaching methodologies and also qualified and efficient teachers are needed to enhance the quality in the system of education. Teacher is expected to reach students effectively for transactions of contents together with behavior modification to be complete and hence achieve the goal of quality among learners. Due to the significance of the teacher effectiveness for the system to be effective, the investigator has selected the problem to carry out her study in this field.

Aim of the Study:

The study was aimed to study the teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers.

Sample:

The sample of the study was the higher secondary teachers from different schools in Vellore district, Tamilnadu. The sample was restricted to 300 higher secondary teachers to the investigator for the study. Government, private and aided is considered for the investigation.

Tool:

Teacher Effectiveness Scale by Umme Dixit (1993).

Methodology:

The present investigation is meant to study the teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers from Vellore district. Normative survey method was adopted for the conduct of the present study. The sample consisted of 300 higher secondary teachers randomly selected from Vellore district in Tamilnadu. In order to collect data for the study the tool which was constructed and validated by the investigator to assess the Teacher Effectiveness was used. The tool was arrived with 60 items. It is a five point scale. The five point scale has descriptors as poor, fair, good, very good and excellent. The scores given as 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The subjects are expected to give their opinion on each of the sixty statements. The reliability value of the tool was found as 0.89, and the validity was found to be 0.94.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the difference if any, in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers regard to gender.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers regard to type of management.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers regard to nature of school.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers regard to location of school.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers regard to marital status.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers with regard to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers with regard to type of management.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers with regard to nature of school.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers with regard to location of school.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers with regard to marital status.

Analysis of Data:

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers with regard to gender.

Table 1: ‘t’ test between Male and Female Higher Secondary Teachers towards Teacher Effectiveness

Gender	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	LS
Male	157	136.57	50.37	0.028	NS
Female	143	136.40	58.72		

It is evident from the Table 1, the calculated ‘t’ value is 0.028, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no

significant difference found out between male and female higher secondary teachers with respect to their teacher effectiveness.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers with regard to type of management.

Table 2: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Type of Management towards Teacher Effectiveness

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	LS
Between Groups	30473.228	15236.614	2	5.291	NS
Within Groups	855247.768	2879.622	297		
Total	885720.997		299		

It is evident from the Table 2, the calculated 'F' value is 0.048, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers with regard to nature of school.

Table 3: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Nature of School towards Teacher Effectiveness

Nature of School	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	LS
Between Groups	3606.165	1803.083	2	0.607	NS
Within Groups	882114.832	2970.084	297		
Total	885720.997		299		

It is evident from the Table 3, the calculated 'F' value is 0.607, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of nature of school with respect to their teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers with regard to location of school.

Table 4: 't' test between Rural and urban Higher Secondary Teachers towards Teacher Effectiveness

Location of School	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	LS
Rural	116	141.86	53.11	0.228	NS
Urban	184	133.11	55.11		

It is evident from the Table 4, the calculated 't' value is 0.228, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban higher secondary teachers with respect to their teacher effectiveness.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of higher secondary teachers with regard to marital status

Table 5: 't' test between Married and Unmarried Higher Secondary Teachers towards Teacher Effectiveness

Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	LS
Married	189	136.00	55.28	0.071	NS
Unmarried	111	137.33	53.17		

It is evident from the Table 5, the calculated 't' value is 0.071, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between married and higher secondary teachers with respect to their teacher effectiveness.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ There is a no significant difference between the higher secondary teachers in their teacher effectiveness with regard to their gender.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference between the higher secondary teachers in their teacher effectiveness with regard to their nature of school.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference between the higher secondary teachers in their teacher effectiveness with regard to their nature of school.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference between the higher secondary teachers in their teacher effectiveness with regard to their location of school.

- ✓ There is a no significant difference between the higher secondary teachers in their teacher effectiveness with regard to their marital status.

Suggestions and Scope of Further Research:

On the basis of this study the investigator forwards some suggestive measures to attain teacher effectiveness among all groups of teachers. Teachers should be recruited through a proper channel and effective policy. Teacher student ratio should be in proper shape. Pay scale, working environment, promotional benefits, after service benefits must be upgraded. Part time and contractual teachers should get job security as well as proper pay scale according to their qualification and work load. The same study could be carried out on teachers from different streams, both in school and college level. Comparative studies could be made to find out the life satisfaction level of regular and distance course teachers also.

Delimitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is confined to measure the teacher effectiveness only.
- ✓ This study has been restricted only to the higher secondary teachers in Government, government, aided and private,
- ✓ This study is carried out taking 300 teachers as sample

Recommendations for the Present Study:

- ✓ Skill based workshops, conferences and seminars must be organized periodically to develop these skills in these areas.
- ✓ Psychological skill based activities to be promoted in teacher education institutions to promote the teaching among the teachers.
- ✓ Practical sessions to be given much more importance to develop the teaching among the teachers.
- ✓ Quality of the programme has to be still more improved to develop the teaching effectiveness of the teachers.

Conclusion:

The present study showed that higher secondary teacher's teacher effectiveness towards school level. Teaching is a unique profession that leads to betterment of the society, making of good human being and responsible citizens. Teachers have to perform this strenuous duty with utmost care and expertise. Therefore, their personal effectiveness regarding teaching and other factors related to it is very important.

References:

1. Alex Moore. The Good Teacher: Dominant discourses in Teaching and Teacher Education.
2. Anju Kalita (2012). A study on managing effectiveness of secondary school teachers in
3. Best John, W., & Khan, James, V. (2008) Research in Education, Tenth Edition, New Delhi. Prentice Hall of India Private Ltd.
4. Fatima Islahi & Nasreen (2013). Who make effective teachers, Men or Women? An Indian Perspective. Universal Journal of Educational Research, 1(4), 285-293.
5. Garrett, Henry & Wood Worth, R.S. (2008). Statistics in Psychology and Education, Surjeet Publications Ltd, New Delhi.
6. Guilford. J.P (1956) "Fundamental Statistics in Psychology and Education" New York, Mc Graw Hill Book Company Inc.
7. Guwahati city, India. The Clarion international Multidisciplinary Journal, 1(2), 238-241.
8. James H. Strange, Pamela D. Tucker, & Jennifer L. Hindman. Handbook for Qualities of Effective Teachers
9. Lokesh Koul (1990) Methodology of Educational Research (2nd Ed) New Delhi, Vikas Publishing house Pvt. Ltd.,
10. Renjith Kumar, R. & Fezeena Khadir (2013). A Study on Teaching Effectiveness of Self-Financing Engineering College Teachers in Kerala. International Journal of Asian Social Science, 3(1): 1- 9.